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Safety Assurance Techniques for the Development of a Rail Industry Safety Case

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KEYWORDS

Goal Structuring Notation;
Safety Risk Assessment;
Automatic Train Protection;
Safety Case;
Safety Assurance.

ABSTRACT

This research paper addresses the shortcomings of the Goal Structuring Notation (GSN), which has been deployed in many safety cases, including the railway and other industries such as health care, oil and gas, and aviation.

The GSN is a graphical presentation that has been deployed to present the safety argument in the case. However, the GSN does not provide a substantiated safety analysis method in itself. The lack of concreteness in GSN presents several limitations in safety analysis, including self-fulfilling prophecy, false confidence, a focus on process rather than property, and difficulties in identifying omissions.

This research paper employed a qualitative research method to investigate the research problem through five major case studies. The findings highlighted that safety assurance activities must be integrated into the system lifecycle, from design through implementation, operation, and maintenance. The main safety assurance tasks are safety risk assessments, which shall be undertaken to identify foreseeable hazards and either eliminate or manage them to a level So Far as Is Reasonably Practicable (SFAIRP). Moreover, during the research, it was also noted that high technology, such as Automatic Train Protection (ATP), undermines the concept of safety causation models, including the Domino and Swiss Cheese models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Railways are considered a relatively high-safety-risk industry for end users, with injuries and fatalities when accidents occur. Therefore, safety plays a critical function in the operation of systems. Over the last century, it is believed that the focus on safety has been purely on technological malfunctions, with limited recognition of the complexity of human interaction in the developed system. However, the new generation of safety thinking emerged in the latter part of the 20th century, driven by technological advances. As such, the new generation of safety thinking is now shifted with the focus on the system view of the proposed design system, with the mindset of system integration of social-technical engineering with the existing systems, including the interaction of people, community, and technology in workplaces to deliver the system's safety function over its life.

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Figure 1 illustrates the context of a railway system from a system's perspective.

Figure 1. Context of the Railway System (Author-developed model)

The Rail Safety National Law, NSW (2012), and the Occupational Health and Safety Act (2011) are applicable in Sydney, Australia. They prescribe the health, safety, and welfare standards for workers involved in NSW works operations such as planning, design, construction, commissioning, and asset service and maintenance. Safety cases have been applied and are generally well recognised in both the United Kingdom and Australia in relation to the above legal requirements.

1.1 Context of the safety case

Rail system certification in Sydney, Australia, is based on a safety case that determines whether a new construction system (system configuration change) to the current rail network reduces safety risks to a reasonable degree, so far as is reasonably practicable (SFAIRP). Both technological and social subsystems, such as individuals, hardware, applications, servicing, and the environment in which the asset(s) will be installed, must be discussed in the safety scenario. Safety cases, according to Leveson, are usually used to assess possible risks in a project and put risk-mitigation mechanisms in place to mitigate the risk (Leveson, 1995). Rowe points out that safety will affect an event's unintended negative effects (Rowe, 1987).

Risk can be interpreted in several ways. For example, financial risk is characterised as the difference between returns on equity and cash flow. Simultaneously, the safety risk is related to the probability and implications of failure to achieve the realistic safety goal, schedule, and performance goals. Safety risks, on the other hand, cannot be seen in isolation from other programmatic issues, such as financial, scheduling, expense, and performance risks, since all of these have an effect on system safety. Safety is characterised as avoiding an accident, with an accident defined as damages incurred by an unforeseen incident with a negative result (Leveson, 1995; Hollnagel, 2005).

To improve safety performance, it is critical to understand the factors contributing to the accident's occurrence. As per Leveson (2004), accidents occurred in the complex social system due to unexpected interactions in multiple systems and subsystems rather than in a single subsystem that had experienced

failure. According to Leveson, the safety risk in a system is the association of hazard level, hazard exposure, and the likelihood of hazard leading to an accident, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Risk Components (Author-developed model)

1.2 Safety case approach

According to a literature review, there have been several approaches to carrying out safety cases, including (1) goal performance-based and (2) prescriptive process. In the United Kingdom, the goal performance-based (goal structuring notation [GSN]) approach to developing safety cases is widely used (Kelly and McDermid, 1998). Kelly specifies that a Safety Case should include three main components: “(1) safety requirements, (2) safety argument, and (3) safety evidence” (Kelly, 2004, p.258). Kelly defined an argument as “how someone can reasonably conclude that a system is acceptably safe based on the evidence available” (Kelly, 2004), as illustrated in Figure 3, shows how safety requirements are supported by specific claims and how they are supported by evidence in the context of the defined scope for the argument.

Figure 3. The Role of Safety Argumentation

Note: Adapted from “A systematic approach to safety case management” by T. Kelly, 2004, International in SAE International Journal of Advances and Current Practices in Mobility Vol. 1, Page 258 (<https://doi.org/10.4271/2004-01-1779>). Copyright 2004 by Publisher SAE.

In the rail sector of Sydney, Australia, the Goal Structuring Notation (GSN) method is commonly used to develop a safety case. The GSN, on the other hand, falls short of providing a structured safety engineering approach for conducting the safety assessment and analysis, as well as an adequate level of reliability assurance for the designed system.

The GSN is a “graphical argumentation notation” that can be deployed to generate a safety case (Kelly, 2003). The GSN diagrams do not demonstrate how the proof goals and sub-goals can be grouped and argued to support the safety claim; instead, they show how the evidence items can be combined and argued to support the safety claim. The GSN is made up of five parts: (1) objective, (2) meaning, (3) claim technique, (4) proof, and (5) relationships between these parts. The GSN uses this approach to

show how particular criteria are supported by factual statements and facts within the argument's given framework. The method of constructing a GSN can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Construction of the safety argument based on the GSN approach (Author-generated model)

1.3 Limitations of Goal Structuring Notation (GSN)

Kelly (2010) provides an example of safety in a software-intensive system scenario (see Figure 5).

When examining figure 5 shows the two components, G8 and G9 goals are involved in the conclusion that “unintended opening press can only occur as a result of component failure.” The evidence supports both G8 and G9, as shown by:

- Fault tree analysis
- Hazard directed test results

It is concluded that there are no software hazards, and hence the control system logic is free from any fault.

Fault trees are used to classify component faults that occur in injuries, according to the reasons given in G8 and G9. On the other side, fault trees may be mistaken. Furthermore, even though they are correct, they can only show “failure”; no proof of finding “design flaws” or “product” encounters that could lead to the top failure has been found. The software’s function in injuries must be regarded in terms of system architecture and software specifications, not component failure (Leveson, 2003 and Leveson, 2004). The fault trees are imperfect, and there is no proof to show that the accidental opening will only occur due to the fault trees of a component failure.

On the other hand, the second point is much worse, and checking will never prove that this won't happen (Leveson, 2003 and 2004). It can only show that it did not occur during the testing environment, however. It should be remembered that the testing environment could not be representative of the real world. As a result, there are flaws in the testing. According to Leveson, it is common to conclude that the accidental opening of the press could occur in a typical device safety review. Then the safety analyst could describe all the situations in which this could happen (Leveson, 2003 and 2004). The goal of the exercise is to find potential software hazards and apply measures to prevent the accidents rather than demonstrating that the software hazards are non-existent or do not exist, as appears in the case. A safety analyst's goal, according to Leveson, is to show that the built system is unsafe, which is precisely opposite to the engineers, who have always strived to develop safety systems and perform verification to demonstrate that they are safe (Leveson, 2003 and 2004).

In conclusion, the preceding literature, assessment and analysis have demonstrated that using the GNS method fails to apply a structured approach in the development of the safety case. In addition, the GSN method lacks sufficient reliability to conclude that the system is safe to operate in a given operating context.

Figure 5. An example of the safety case for the software-intensive system

Note: Adapted from "A Systematic Approach for Developing Software Safety Arguments" by T. Kelly, et al., 2010, 27th International System Safety Conference, Page 2. Copyright 2010 by International System Safety Conference.

Context – the context needs to be included as it explains the assumptions and justification for the Goal.

Strategy – the strategy explains the relationship between Goal and set of Sub-goals or between a Goal and the solutions or evidence.

Link – A link element is used to identify the subsequent diagram/s. Link/s is used where required to split diagrams into sections that suit the purpose of the analysis.

Evidence – evidence (e.g., solution) is used to support the goal. Evidence can be presented in various forms, namely product information, process information, test results, analysis, and audit results.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1 Research Questions

The research questions in this study were as follows:

- What is a structured approach for the development of the safety case?
- How does the structured approach improve the outcome of the safety case?

2.2 Research Approach

This project used a qualitative approach to address the research questions (Creswell, 2006) and was grounded in a descriptive case study design. The qualitative data were collected from the five case studies using the “checklist”. The five case studies enabled the researcher to explore safety practices and controls for managing safety risks within the selected organisations, resulting in the production of safety cases. The five case studies are sufficient for this research project. The investigator explored the research issues through various lenses, revealing and understanding multiple facets of the safety practice and safety controls phenomenon (Yin, 2003).

The research project aimed to better understand the components associated with safety case production using a structured engineering approach. Therefore, the data collection from the five descriptive case studies and analysis focused on the “what,” “when,” “how,” and “why” of the safety activities and hazard analysis techniques undertaken to support the safety argument presented in the safety case.

Content validity is essential to qualitative data collection (Guion, 1978). In this context, the “checklist” ensured the credibility of the findings of the study. Additionally, the researcher ensured that the interpretation of the collected data was consistent and transparent to avoid personal biases that may have influenced the findings. Furthermore, this approach was shown by comparing the *five case studies*, seeking similarities and differences across accounts to ensure that perspectives are represented.

The initial step of the content analysis was to read the documents (*five case studies*) to gain a general understanding of them. Next, the data was grouped into the category as per the “checklist”. Following that, the researcher wrote down the initial impressions of the documents: What stands out? What are the discrepancies, and what are the similarities? What are their relationships (i.e., assumptions, dependencies, and constraints with safety implications? Finally, with this in mind, the researcher looked for a complete safety activity and analysis techniques documented in the *five case studies* (Erlingsson & Brysiewicz, 2017).

2.3 Research Justifications

The reason for selecting the *case studies* was that they provided rich information and a comprehensive research investigation of the safety practices and components associated with safety case production, which addressed this project’s *research questions 1 and 2*. Therefore, the findings of the case studies are beneficial as they provide practical improvement applications for the railway’s safety practitioners. In addition, the case studies provide insights into phenomena that cannot be explored or identified using other methods (Yin, 2011). In addition, Milesi et al. (2007) noted that the rationale for having the case studies is that this research project’s aims and objectives are exploratory and innovative, requiring greater understanding and analysis of the research investigation. Remarkably, there is little published work on safety cases; hence case studies are the best option for this research project (Marc Milesi et al., 2007).

3. RESULTS

The findings highlighted that safety risk assessments should be undertaken to capture all potential hazards. A summary of the case studies is described in the below sections:

3.1 Case study #1 – Bow-tie Analysis

It is a well-known fact that the railway industry presents a number of high safety risks, including (1) train collisions due to overspeed limits resulting in derailment, (2) level crossing collisions where trains and public passengers interact, and so on. It should be noted that train derailments can have various potential causes. These possible causes are drivers' errors, signal sighting obstruction, fallen trees or objects left on the track, and broken tracks due to inadequate maintenance.

This case study examined the derailment risk assessment conducted by the Project. It has been identified that there is a risk of derailment on high embankments due to the lack of shoulder width of the track slab containing a derailed train. Train derailment poses a significant safety risk to railways; therefore, all railways must conduct risk assessments for it.

Derailment is an undesirable phenomenon that can damage rolling stock and infrastructure and cause service disruptions. It might also cause casualties and harm the environment. Moreover, these effects might result in serious reputational and financial losses for railway operators and organisations, as well as social, psychological, and economic consequences for the public.

This risk mitigation strategy (derailment risk assessment) supported the safety argument presented in the Safety Assurance Report (also known as Safety Case).

The case study #1 highlights the benefits of using the bow-tie risk assessment, including:

3.1.1 *Visual clarity and communication*

- **Simplifies complexity:** The bowtie diagram provides a single, easy-to-understand picture of a risk, making complex scenarios much clearer than a standard risk matrix.
- **Improves communication:** It creates a common language for risk across the entire organisation, from engineers to management, which increases risk awareness and understanding.
- **Illustrates cause and effect:** It visually links threats and their causes on one side (left) to the consequences and their potential impacts on the other (right), showing how an incident can unfold.

3.1.2 *Proactive risk management*

- **Highlights controls:** It clearly shows the control measures (barriers) that are in place to prevent threats from escalating and to mitigate the consequences if they do.
- **Identifies gaps:** The method helps identify weaknesses in existing controls and can highlight areas where new or enhanced controls are needed to create a more complete risk picture.
- **Supports decision-making:** The clear visualization aids in making decisions about risk management and allocating resources effectively.

3.1.3 Incident investigation and assurance

- **Supports root cause analysis:** Bowtie analysis can be used to support incident investigations, helping to identify what went wrong, what barriers failed, and what changes are needed to prevent recurrence.
- **Provides assurance:** It can be used as an audit tool to check if barriers are working as intended and consistently.

3.2 Case study #2 – Reliability, Availability, Maintainability (RAM)

The RAM assessment has been prepared for the Station Fire System. In evaluating the RAM performance of the Fire System design, the following RAM activities are undertaken as part of the RAM assessment:

- Establish System Operation
- Development of System Breakdown Structure (SBS)
- Identification of Lowest Replaceable Units (LRU)
- Functional Analysis
- Failure Mode, Effects and Criticality Analysis (FMECA)
- Reliability Block Diagram (RBD)
- Maintainability Analysis

3.2.1 Reliability

In performing a reliability assessment of a design package, the content of the package was considered in the context of a reliable rail service. If a failure of the design would directly impact the ability to operate trains, then the analysis would include high-level single points of failure (SPoFs) and common cause failures (CCFs) (where applicable). Any SPoFs/ CCFs identified, are assessed to determine how the design has specifically considered reliability.

It is to be noted that the design of static assets such as track, overhead structures, and civil structures, for which longevity, durability, and maintainability are more applicable concepts than the typical RAM characteristics.

3.2.2 Maintainability

The approach to assessing maintainability is to consider the actions required to perform maintenance, the ability to perform those actions, and the maintenance frequency.

It is to be noted that the maintainability analysis included a list of relevant access and maintainability requirements. For example, a graphical reliability block diagram (RBD) may be presented for the selected asset to show the criticality of rail services.

The RAM Issues Log records all considerations given or complications encountered regarding reliability and maintainability as the design stages progress.

Demonstrate how and to what extent the RAM requirements are incorporated in the design, including use/re-use of type-approved equipment, compliance with the relevant standards, and the possibility of having waivers where deviations from the standards are present.

It should be noted that maintainability has been considered in the Safety Assurance workshops and RAM assessment (desktop assessments) for all design options, including type-approved, to ensure the potential safety risks and environmental risk conditions associated with the proposed design solutions are managed to a level SFAIRP.

3.2.3 Availability

Availability, by definition, is a function of reliability and maintainability. No availability analysis was done on the design packages without availability targets. Once a design has been analysed for the best outcomes in terms of reliability and maintainability, this will flow through to the best achievable availability.

Once the systems, boundaries, and RAM requirements are defined, the key process step is to perform an FMECA for each contributing subsystem. The outputs from these elements provide the data required to construct the Reliability Block Diagram (RBD) for the system, where applicable. The RBDs and the preceding activities provided information on complications such as single points of failure (SPoF), common cause failures (CCF), etc., for assessment and feedback on the designs, and for a qualitative review of the designs via the forum RAM System Review (RSR). The RAM Issues Log captured design issues and associated treatments. The RSRs of the design were typically assessed how the design (as a minimum):

- Contributes towards operational performance and service delivery.
- Reduces the risk associated with reliability-critical items.
- Minimises or eliminates single points of failure.
- Supports ease of maintenance.
- Lifecycle cost impacts.

The RSR and feedback may lead to design changes to improve RAM. The analysis results can also be used to evaluate the impacts of design changes.

For design packages where a detailed analysis is required but the system is still considered a relevant contributor to a reliable and punctual rail service, a high-level RBD is conducted to support a qualitative assessment of the design.

Once a system design is finalised, a reliability-centred maintenance (RCM) process is used to determine its maintenance strategies and requirements.

It is noted that the signalling subsystems with RAM implications and packages not based on defined design standards or specifications were analysed in detail as required. Where data is available, a comparative analysis is done between the existing arrangement and the proposed design to assess reliability and maintainability implications. When the design introduces new components or materials, the appropriate method for developing maintenance strategies is used to determine the actions and activities required.

The analysis shows no failure modes identified in the FMECA that could impact train services. Therefore, the station fire system design is not considered to contribute to the overall train service availability and reliability performance targets. No SPoF items have been identified for the Fire system. At the same time, fifteen components are considered RCI, and the looping design has sufficiently provided a high level of inherent reliability to reduce local risks upon failure.

The maintainability of the fire system is well defined in Australia Standard AS1851, which details servicing schedules, tasks, and test activities for each component of the fire system. Spare parts requirements are also provided in the Fire System Specification, which details the expected inventory level for each part based on its criticality and the impact of its failure. This RAM assessment supports the operational requirements and technical maintenance plan for the railway operations.

3.3 Case study #3 – Ergonomics assessment

The Pedestrian Egress bridge is intended for emergencies only and will not be accessible for everyday use. This bridge is designed to provide emergency egress from the station, and therefore, access to the bridge will be closed at both ends. The bridge design does not include certain features of the Active Transport Link bridge, such as lighting posts and handrails. The bridge only has balustrades, with an approximate height of 1500 mm.

A climb ability assessment was undertaken to evaluate the physical demands of climbing-related tasks in relation to human capabilities, incorporating ergonomic principles and anthropometric measurements.

The climb ability assessment revealed that, barring any mobility impairments, almost all adults and most children aged 6 and older would be able to climb onto the handrail and cycle rail of the Active Transport Link bridge, and onto the balustrades of the Pedestrian Egress bridge. Climbing may be difficult for people smaller than the 95%M, but could be achieved with sufficient motivation, strength and biomechanical capabilities. The bridge design does not provide footholds or handholds; however, the railings and lighting posts could be used to assist with climbing onto the bridge wall structure for the Active Transport Link bridge.

There is a safety risk of entrapment for children on the Pedestrian Egress bridge, as there is no mesh behind the balustrades. Providing mesh would assist in preventing entrapment; however, the so far as is reasonably practical (SFAIRP) approach should be used to determine whether mesh should be provided for this bridge. The bridge is to be used only during emergencies, and protection screens are to be provided for the bridge when the railway line is constructed under it in the future.

This assessment evaluates whether it would be possible to climb onto the bridge wall structure, from an anthropometric and biomechanical perspective, in relation to bridge design. Sufficient controls to prevent climbing should be provided so far as is reasonably practical (SFAIRP).

Climb ability (or the assessment of interacting with structures like stairs or ladders) is a specific application of physical ergonomics.

Assessment Process: This involves analysing the physical demands of climbing, such as the required force, posture, and movement, relative to human physical capabilities.

Key Factors: Assessments consider factors like the optimal and critical dimensions of stairs (riser height, tread depth), the user's body morphology (e.g., leg length, flexibility), and potential physical limitations due to age or health conditions (e.g., obesity).

Ergonomics assessment enhances safety mitigations and reduces the likelihood of safety risks of the railway operation assets.

3.4 Case study #4 – Safety Integrity Level (SIL)

Functional safety is an essential element of overall safety that relies on equipment and systems responding appropriately to inputs. Additionally, it assures that the systems will operate in a predictable

and regulated manner (fail-safe) in the case of a malfunction. It guarantees that malfunctions in software, hardware, or even human operation are found and fixed, reducing risk to a manageable level.

Functional safety in railways refers to a system's ability to respond in ways that ensure the safety of personnel, property, and equipment in the event of an emergency. These automatic protection systems must be appropriately built to manage operational and environmental stress, hardware failures, systematic errors, and likely human errors.

A number of principles form the foundation of functional safety:

Risk assessment and reduction: After hazards are recognised and assessed, systems are created to lower risks to manageable levels, SFAIRP.

System response to failure: The design ensures that the system either maintains or moves to a safe state in the event of a failure.

Lifetime approach: Design, development, operation, maintenance, and decommissioning are all lifetime phases where safety is important.

Safety Integrity Levels (SIL): The degree of risk reduction necessary determines the classification of safety functions.

SIL which measures the dependability of certain safety functions is based on this structure. This case study examines the application of SIL assessment in the railway (Light Rail (LR)) context.

The SIL requirements from the identified Tolerable Hazard Rates for the applicable safety functions shall be derived as per AS 61508 and deliver a safety function as per BS EN 50126-2:2017. These SIL requirements have been developed and allocated to each system in this document using SIL allocation techniques such as the calibrated Risk Graph Methodology.

Safety integrity level (SIL) is defined as a relative level of risk-reduction provided by a safety function, or to specify a target level of risk reduction. In simple terms, SIL measures the performance required for a safety instrumented function (SIF).

The requirements for a given SIL are inconsistent among all the functional safety standards. Based on the IEC 61508 standard, the functional safety standards define four SILs, with SIL 4 being the most dependable and SIL 1 being the least. The applicable SIL is determined based on several quantitative and qualitative factors, including the development process and safety lifecycle management.

The Safety Integrity Levels are discrete levels defined to specify safety requirements for safety-related functions carried out by E/E/PE systems. A given SIL between SIL 1 and SIL 4 is linked to qualitative and quantitative requirement specifications for a safety-related function defined according to the random and systematic failures related to the E/E/PE safety-related systems that perform the function. SIL 4 is associated with the most demanding requirements to counteract the hazards caused by these two types of failures. SIL 0 is occasionally defined for tasks with no safety requirements. Appropriate assurance must be provided throughout the design, inspection, testing, and commissioning phases to validate compliance with safety integrity level requirements.

A SIL is usually associated with a system function or a subsystem and is used for two purposes: first, a specific SIL provides an interval for the rate of safety-critical failures. This characteristic applies to so-called "Random Faults", i.e. failures that occur unpredictably. These faults are mainly caused by intrinsic physical processes such as ageing. Second, a SIL defines measures to be applied during design and manufacturing to keep the frequency of so-called "Systematic Faults" low compared to that of random faults. The cause of systematic faults is mainly a design or manufacturing process error that leads to

failures in identical replications of the same component or equipment under similar circumstances. These faults might also reveal themselves in the form of common cause failures.

The higher the SIL, the harder the requirements for the system function. Therefore, defining a SIL for a function or equipment is essential. This is done in two steps: Define a tolerable hazard rate. Use a SIL table to identify the SIL from the tolerable hazard rate. The SIL table indicates an interval for tolerable hazard rates for each SIL. One note needs to be added on applying a SIL to components, modules, sub-systems, and systems. EN 50129 requires defining the SIL for a system function, not for components, modules, or other constituents. Therefore, the SIL may be determined only for a system function.

This case study demonstrates that SIL plays a crucial safety function role in the safety-critical system. SIL quantifies and reduces safety risk by adding an additional layer of safety, detecting potential failures and mitigating them. The four levels of SIL, see Figure 6, must be integrated into the design system as required. The highest SIL level is suitable for a safety-critical system. It should be noted that the cost associated with the highest SIL can be substantial as it requires a robust testing and certification process, and therefore, choosing the correct SIL level is essential.

Figure 6. Safety Integrity Level (Author-generated figure)

SIL is a good tool for mitigating the safety risks in the railway. The likelihood of a safety function failing on demand (PFD) is used to define SIL. PFD is the likelihood that a safety function won't carry out its mandated safety function when it's called upon. The SIL increases as the risk of failure decreases. A likelihood of dangerous failure per hour can also be utilised for continuous operations, such as industrial processes. In complex socio-technical systems, SIL safety applications must function in diverse environments. For example, SIL safety applications enhance the overall safety of the railway operations, including monitoring the trains' speed and movements, and applying the braking distance appropriately in reducing the risk of accidents such as derailments.

3.5 Case study #5 – Systems-Theoretic Process Analysis

The Automated Train Protection (ATP) system is a safe critical system that accurately captures track and train-related data. It uses that data to implement operational speed monitoring and excessive speed protection, ensuring the train's safety while in operation. Figure 7 illustrates communication-based train control, which is the system that manages the traffic and infrastructure, which comprises continuous communication between trains and a central control system. The communication-based train control system consists of the following subsystems:

Figure 7. Communication-based train control hierarchy (Author-generated figure)

Automatic Train Supervision (ATS)- A system called Automatic Train Supervision (ATS) keeps an eye on and manages a rail network to make sure trains follow a predetermined timetable and traffic pattern. To do this, it automatically routes trains, makes real-time adjustments to operations, and controls train movements to maximise dependability and performance. It also logs activities and reports system status.

Automatic Train Operation (ATO) - In order to increase productivity, timeliness, and passenger comfort, Automatic Train Operation (ATO) automates train driving duties like braking, halting, and accelerating. To control train movements, maximise traffic flow, and uphold safety. It integrates with other systems such as Automatic Train Protection (ATP) and Automatic Train Supervision (ATS).

ATO equipment is a non-essential equipment that is mostly mounted on board and offers features for autonomous driving. It ensures the train will maintain the speed profile without abrupt changes in acceleration and braking phases under the direction of the ATP system, stop at stations or in front of a stop signal in the proper position, and open and close the doors on the right side while confirming the train's location at a station and that it would notify the control centre of the train's condition. Although **ATO** systems are now mostly used in metro networks and situations like trains at airport terminals, their deployment on main and suburban lines is becoming more feasible as train control technologies advance. Signalling and train control systems must be improved for ATO systems to be widely deployed.

Automatic Train Protection (ATP) - To prevent accidents, Automatic Train Protection (ATP) keeps track of a train's direction, speed, and distance. It provides the train with speed and signalling information via trackside devices, such as electronic transponders known as balises. The train can be safely stopped by the system automatically applying the brakes if the driver goes over the allowed speed limit or ignores warnings.

3.5.1 Findings

- How does automatic train protection (ATP) improve rail safety and efficiency?

The automatic train protection (ATP) enhances rail safety by preventing trains from exceeding speed limits and ensuring adherence to signals. By monitoring train speed and intervening, when necessary, ATP helps prevent accidents caused by human error or signal misinterpretation. Additionally, ATP can allow for closer spacing between trains, improving operational efficiency without compromising safety.

- What are the key differences between automatic train protection (ATP) and positive train control (PTC), and how do they complement each other?

While both automatic train protection (ATP) and positive train control (PTC) focus on enhancing rail safety, they differ in scope and technology. ATP primarily focuses on speed regulation and adherence to signals, intervening when trains exceed safe limits. PTC incorporates GPS data and communication systems to prevent accidents by automatically slowing or stopping. Together, they create a comprehensive safety framework that addresses various potential hazards in rail operations.

- Evaluate the impact of implementing automatic train protection (ATP) systems on the overall operational dynamics of rail networks.

The implementation of automatic train protection (ATP) systems significantly transforms the operational dynamics of rail networks by enhancing safety protocols and enabling more efficient scheduling. With reduced incidents caused by human error, operators can maintain tighter schedules and increase service frequency without compromising passenger safety. Moreover, as trains can run closer together under the guidance of ATP systems, rail networks can accommodate higher traffic volumes while optimising resource allocation, ultimately leading to improved service reliability and customer satisfaction. The ATP systems typically involve a combination of trackside and onboard equipment, as alluded to in the following:

Onboard Equipment: Includes an onboard computer, wheel speed sensors, an antenna, and a driver machine interface (DMI) to display information to the driver.

Trackside Equipment: Includes components like balises (small passive transponders on the track) or other electronic units that transmit data to the train.

Data Transmission: Information about train location, speed limits, and signal aspects is transmitted from the trackside to the onboard computer.

Safety Enforcement: If the train exceeds a speed limit or passes a red signal, the onboard computer automatically applies the brakes to bring the train to a safe stop.

3.5.2 Benefits of ATP

The benefits of ATP are as follows:

Accident Prevention: The primary benefit is the prevention of accidents caused by human error, signal violations, or other unforeseen circumstances.

Enhanced Safety: Systems like Kavach are Safety Integrity Level (SIL)-4 certified, indicating a very high level of safety and an exceptionally low probability of error.

Improved Efficiency: ATP systems contribute to increased reliability, punctuality, and operational efficiency.

Collision Avoidance: The system monitors train movements and can prevent collisions between two trains equipped with the functional ATP system.

In summary, Systems-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) is a tool that can be used to evaluate complex socio-technical systems, particularly those involving computer and software systems associated with railway signalling, namely Automated Train Protection (ATP), is a well-known safety-critical accident-prevention technology. In this context, traditional hazard analysis techniques such as FTA, FMEA, and ETA focus on potential causes of component failures or faults that result in accidents. These techniques overlook the complex socio-technical systems that involve many interconnected parts, e.g., software, technology, rules, human behaviour, and the context of operational environments. This oversight has led

to incomplete hazard management, and therefore the STPA method has gone beyond traditional safety techniques that overlook essential causes of accidents in complex socio-technical systems, namely flawed software requirements, dysfunctional component interactions, and software errors.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper suggested that safety assurance activities should be an integral part of the design and that conducting safety risk assessments, as outlined in Table 1, would enhance and support the safety argument presented in the Safety Assurance Report (Safety Case).

Table 1 indicates the conditions under which it may be appropriate to use the indicative techniques and shows some of the indicative methods that can be used. The choice of technique(s) should be based on the purpose of the analysis - *known/unknown causes and consequences*.

Table 1. How to determine the technique to use based on the purpose of the analysis methods (Author-generated table)?

<p>Comprehension</p> <p>Case Studies #1 and #2</p> <p>FMEA/FMECA, Bow-Tie Analysis</p>	<p>Consequence Analysis</p> <p>Event Tree Analysis – Case Studies 3 and 4</p>
<p>Causal Analysis</p> <p>Ergonomics Assessment – Case Study 3, Bow-Tie Analysis</p>	<p>Exploratory Analysis</p> <p>RBDs, STPA – Case Studies 2 and 5</p>

4.1 Suggestion of the Lifecycle Safety Assurance Activities

The System Safety activities should be developed in alignment with the System Safety Lifecycle, as illustrated in Figure 8, to support the progression, approval, and implementation of the network change.

The following sections describe the details of the Safety Assurance activities in alignment with the System Safety Lifecycle, including (1) Concept, (2) System Definition, (3) System Requirements and Design, (4) System Build and Validation, (5) Operation and Maintenance, and (6) Decommissioning and Disposal.

Figure 8. System Safety Lifecycle (Author-generated figure)

At the Concept Stage, the primary objective of Safety Assurance is to undertake optioneering of the proposed design solutions and identify the RAM requirements associated with each option per Table 2.

Table 2. Safety Assurance activities at Concept (Author-generated table)

Safety Activities	Safety Assessment Outcome - Impact Level		
	High Risk	Medium Risk	Low Risk
Risk assessment of options	M	M	M
RAM Requirements (where applicable)	M	M	O
M= Mandatory; O = Optional			

The purpose of the System Definition is to establish the intended Safety Assurance approach so that safety risks can be identified, analysed, controlled, and verified throughout the System Safety Lifecycle, as per Table 3.

Table 3. Safety Assurance activities at System Definition. Author-generated table (Author-generated table)

Safety Activities	Safety Assessment Outcome - Impact Level		
	High Risk	Medium Risk	Low Risk
Complete a Safety Change Assessment	M	M	M
Appoint a System Safety Manager for the project	M	M	M
Appoint an Independent Safety Assessor (ISA)	M	M	M
Prepare a Safety Assurance Plan (SAP)	M	M	M
Outline the safety argument in the SAP.	M	M	M
Conduct a Preliminary Hazard Analysis (PHA)	M	M	M
Initiate a Project Hazard Log (PHL)	M	M	M
Define top-level safety requirements.	M	M	NR
RAM Requirements (Where applicable)	O	O	O
Prepare a Safety Assurance Report, including SFAIRP demonstration	M	M	M
Independent Verification (Independent Safety Assessor (ISA)) is mandatory when a SAR is prepared	M#	M	M
Safety Assurance Committee to undertake Safety Review	M	M	M
Prepare SAR	M	M	M
M= Mandatory; NR = Not Required; O = Optional; # ISA required			

The purpose of the *System Requirements and Design* is to conduct a detailed safety risk assessment throughout its System Safety Lifecycle, as outlined in Table 4.

Table 4. Safety Assurance activities associated with System Requirements and Design (Author-generated table)

Safety Activities	Safety Assessment Outcome - Impact Level		
	High Risk	Medium Risk	Low Risk
Manage and maintain a Safety Assurance Plan	M	M	M
Maintain and manage a Project Hazard Log	M	M	M
Conduct hazard identification	M	M	M
Conduct System Hazard Analysis (SHA). Also, refer to Table 1 for selecting the appropriate tool, e.g., FMECA/ETA/Ergonomics/STPA.	M	M	NR
Conduct Interface Hazard Analysis (IHA) if the system has interfaces. Also, refer to Table 1 for selecting the appropriate tool, e.g., FMECA/ETA/Ergonomics/STPA.	M	M	NR
Conduct Operational Support Hazard Analysis (OSHA). Also, refer to Table 1 for selecting the appropriate tool, e.g., FMECA/ETA/Ergonomics/STPA.	M	M	NR
Assess safety claims made by an external party via the Independent Safety Assessment (ISA)	M#	NR	NR
Actively manage the effective interaction between safety and design functions.	M	M	NR
Apply appropriate Human Factors Engineering methods	M	O	NR
RAM Requirements	M	M	O
Develop a design solution that reduces safety risk to a level SFAIRP with justification (through options analysis and development of controls)	M	M	M
Provide safety input into the operational procedures (where applicable)	O	O	O
Conduct Operational Readiness Safety Verification	M	M	O
Prepare a Safety Assurance Report, including an SFAIRP demonstration; ISA is mandatory when a SAR is prepared.	M#	O	O
Safety Assurance Committee to undertake Safety Review	M	M	M
Prepare SAR	M	M	M
M= Mandatory; NR = Not Required; O = Optional; # ISA required			

The purpose of the *System Build and Validation* is to manage safety change activities during the build (construction) throughout the System Safety Lifecycle, as per Table 5.

Table 5. Safety Assurance activities associated with System Build and Validation (Author-generated table)

Safety Activities	Safety Assessment Outcome - Impact Level		
	High Risk	Medium Risk	Low Risk
Maintain and manage a Project Hazard Log (PHL)	M	M	M
Identify and transfer risks to the End User (Where applicable)	M	M	M
Manage changes to design during build, construction and commissioning	M	M	M
Validate safety requirements and record test and validation evidence in the PHL (where safety requirements are defined)	M	M	O
RAM Requirements	M	M	O
Conduct Operational Readiness Safety Verification	M	M	O
Prepare a Safety Assurance Report (SAR) including SFAIRP demonstration	M#	M	M
Prepare a Testing Safety Assurance Report (SAR) including SFAIRP demonstration. IV mandatory where SAR is prepared	M	M	O
Conduct a Pre-Commissioning Review	M	M	O
Achieve safety acceptance by Client acceptance authorities	M	M	M
Safety Assurance Committee to undertake Safety Review	M	M	M
Prepare SAR	M	M	M
M= Mandatory; O = Optional; # ISA required			

The purpose of the *Operations and Maintenance* is to manage safety activities associated with operations and maintenance throughout the System Safety Lifecycle, as per Table 6.

Table 6. Safety Assurance activities associated with Operations and Maintenance (Author generated table)

Safety Activities	Safety Assessment Outcome - Impact Level		
	High Risk	Medium Risk	Low Risk
Close out safety issues from Project Hazard Log (PHL), and SAR/s	M	M	M
Provide PHL (residual Risks) to the End User (where applicable)	M	M	M
Conduct Post-Implementation Review within 6 months of implementation	M	M	O
M= Mandatory; O = Optional			

The purpose of the Decommissioning and Disposal is to manage safety activities associated with Decommissioning and Disposal throughout the System Safety Lifecycle, as per Table 7.

Table 7. Safety Assurance activities associated with Decommissioning and Disposal (Author-generated table)

Safety Activities	Safety Assessment Outcome - Impact Level		
	High Risk	Medium Risk	Low Risk
Undertake safety risk assessment and document foreseeable risks in the PHL	M	M	M
Maintain and manage a Project Hazard Log (PHL)	M	M	M
Provide PHL (residual Risks) to the End User (where applicable)	M	M	M
Safety hazards are documented/ managed via the Decommissioning and Disposal Plan and/or Inspection Test Plans	M	M	M
M= Mandatory			

The proposed structured Safety Assurance approach ensures that all significant hazards are identified, their associated risks assessed, and control measures explicitly defined and supported by evidence. This structured review often reveals gaps in existing safety arrangements, leading to the development and implementation of improvement plans and, ultimately, to a more robust safety system. In summary, the improvement and quality of the Safety Assurance Report (Safety case) include:

Improved Decision-Making: By providing a clear, evidence-based *route map* to safety, a structured safety case supports better-informed decision-making during design, operation, and maintenance. This includes the ability to rapidly evaluate the safety impact of proposed changes (such as cost-saving measures) and justify or prevent them as necessary.

Enhanced Continuous Improvement: Developing a structured safety case fosters a culture of continual assessment and improvement. The clear structure makes the document easier to keep up to date as a “living document,” enabling ongoing monitoring and adaptation to evolving circumstances.

Effective Consultation and Workforce Involvement: The explicit nature of the safety arguments facilitates effective consultation and participation of the workforce and other stakeholders. This collaboration ensures the safety case reflects actual operations, harnesses practical input, and leads to greater understanding and acceptance of the control measures.

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